

Kabiangan: Roles of Women in Woodwork Industry in Binmaley, Pangasinan, Philippines

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ABSTRACT: This study examined the women's roles in the woodworking industry in Binmaley, Pangasinan. It aimed to understand the importance of women's roles and duties, reasons for entering the industry, challenges encountered, coping mechanisms used, and support from the Local Government Unit. Using a qualitative, phenomenological design, researchers selected nine women participants through convenience sampling. Data were collected through in-depth interviews and participant observation. Thematic analysis coding was used to analyze the qualitative data. Findings revealed that women undertook various roles in the woodworking industry, such as managers, marketers, varnishers, sanders, maintenance workers, and polishers but their responsibilities were limited to manufacturing. Men handled heavier tasks like creating wooden products, while women focused on lighter tasks like "paglalaga" or "pagsusuliha" for making rattan furniture. Women entered the industry to contribute to household expenses, inherit a family business, and alleviate poverty. Despite facing demanding customers, work-related hardships, and natural hazards but coped through family support and perseverance. However, they received minimal institutional support, highlighting a gap in assistance programs for women in this sector.

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BACKGROUND

Woodworking refers to creating objects from wood with either hand or power tools. It involves cutting, shaping, carving, and assembling wood components to create a finished product. This field involves making different products using wood and male-dominated as it requires strength and manual labor. Daniel in 2022 mentioned that in Ancient Rome, woodworking contributed to the creation of transportation, tools, furniture, buildings, and more. This also holds historical significance worldwide, with diverse techniques evident in different regions.

A science data team in the United States called Zippia found out that in 2021, there were 92% of male woodworkers and 8% of female woodworkers. As feminist movements emerged, women gained equality, rights, and opportunities which led them to explore different fields such as woodworking (Forgeard, 2023). On the other hand, this study aligns with Sustainable Development Goal 5 (Gender Equality), which aims to achieve gender equality and empower all women and girls (United Nations, 2015). Wood carving is integral to the culture and tradition of communities in the ASEAN Region. In the Philippines, three towns in Luzon are known for their rich woodcarving heritage. These include Hungduan in Ifugao province, (Northern Luzon); Betis and Guagua in Pampanga province, (Central Luzon); and Paete in Laguna province, (Southern Luzon). These communities rely on wood as their primary resource, and it has supported families by providing a source of income and livelihood (Habito et al., n.d.). The Ifugao tribe was a gender-neutral society as both genders were actively involved in economic opportunities. However, hunting and woodcarving were still considered masculine activities due to male strength (Munoz A, 2021).

Moreover, the district of Betis in Guagua, Pampanga, was well-known for its wood carving and to be the furniture-making and woodcarving center not only in Pampanga but throughout Luzon in which many considered Betis furniture being "export quality" and "world class." The old folks who lived in this barangay were believed to be the pioneers in the Kapampangan province's pamandukit (woodcarving) and pamaganluagi (woodworking) traditions (Betis Mandukit: A Comparative Analysis of the Works of Wilfredo Layug and Boyet Flores: Philippine Art, Culture and Antiquities, 2024). Additionally, the research conducted by Piamonte, Pangilinan, Amper, and Carag (2018) in Paete, Laguna, found that in the process of wood carving in Paete, the significant or heavy steps (Padron, Pagbabantso, Pagbabagbag, and Pagdedetalye) were done by men while the last two steps, the Pagkikinis and Pagbabarnis were performed by the women. In the province of Pangasinan, Binmaley is also known for its thriving woodworking

industry, with numerous furniture businesses along Binmaley Road showcasing their exceptional skills and craftsmanship (Pangasinan.gov, 2023).

Furthermore, the word "kabiangan" is a Pangasinan term which means membership (Zorc, R. D., n.d.) or part of a portion or congregation. It also signifies cooperation and teamwork that highlights the collaborative spirit and combined endeavors of individuals accomplish mutual objectives or tasks within a professional environment.

Lastly, this study focused on the duties or the role of women in the woodwork industry, things that led or influenced women to work in a traditionally male-dominated work, challenges encountered by women in their workplace, and how they cope up with it, and also to know the support offered by the Local Government Unit to women in the woodwork industry in Binmaley, Pangasinan.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the women's roles in the woodwork industry in Binmaley, Pangasinan.

Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What were the duties of women in the woodwork industry?
2. What were the reasons influencing women to enter in the woodwork industry?
3. What specific challenges did women encounter within the woodwork sector?
4. What coping mechanisms did women use to address their perceived challenges in the woodwork industry?
5. What support is offered by the Local Government Unit to women in the woodwork industry?

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The researchers used qualitative research method and phenomenological approach to understand the roles of women in the woodwork industry in Binmaley, Pangasinan. Qualitative research sought to understand the depth and nuances of human experiences, perceptions, and actions in their natural setting (Nassaji, 2020). Additionally, Christensen, Johnson, and Turner (2015), said that phenomenology is a "qualitative research method in which the researcher tried to explain how one or more participants experienced a phenomenon (event, situation, concept, etc.)." While Balikçi, A., (2022), explained that, Phenomenology treated reality and experiences individually and was based on the researcher's objectivity as much as possible.

The study focused on women participants in the woodworking industry across various barangays in Binmaley, Pangasinan. These selected barangays, includes Baybay Polong, Malindong, Silag, and Naguilayan, were identified in the list of businesses located within the jurisdiction of Binmaley, Pangasinan, known for their woodworking industry, specifically in furniture making. The chosen sampling method is convenience sampling, where researchers selected nine (9) women participants based on their accessibility and availability to the researcher, ensuring that they met the research objectives. The research technique involves identifying participants based on specific criteria outlined by the researchers. First, the participants of this study were 41 years old and above to ensure they met the qualifications required for their work. Second, participants were required to have at least one year of employment. This criterion aimed to guarantee a depth of experience and perceptions about the women's roles in the woodwork sector. Lastly, this study acknowledged women participants regardless of their educational attainment, civil status, number of children, and income. After selecting the participants, the researchers conducted in-depth interviews with participant observations to gather data and information relevant to the study.

Part I contained the basic information of the participants, such as name (optional), age, marital status, length of employment, educational attainment (optional), number of children, and income.

Part II of the questionnaire focused on the women's roles in the woodwork industry.

Part III of the questionnaire focused on factors influencing the participant to continue working in the industry.

Part IV of the questionnaire focused on identifying the women's challenges in this field.

Part V of the questionnaire focused on identifying the coping mechanisms of women in the woodworking industry in different selected barangays.

Part VI of the questionnaire focused on identifying the support programs implemented by local government units in the specified geographic area.

Overall, these questionnaires served as a guide for the researchers to conduct an in-depth interview with the study participants.

The researchers carried out a series of processes to gather the data required to fulfill the study's goal of constructing questionnaires. The researchers created questionnaires that first validated by the research adviser, followed by five expert validators, to ensure that the prepared questionnaires were valid, well-constructed, and reliable. After validating the research instrument, the researchers formally wrote a letter to the selected barangays—specifically Silag, Baybay Polong, Malindong, and Naguilayan in the municipality of Binmaley—requesting consent to conduct the study and the addresses of the participants to facilitate the distribution of the research instrument, conduct in-depth interviews, and perform participant observations. During the data gathering, the researchers informed the barangays and the participants about the importance of their answers or responses to the study. The researchers ensured the confidentiality of the participants' identities.

The data gathered by the researchers were analyzed throughout the data analysis procedure. They implemented thematic analysis to interpret the qualitative data they collected. According to Mortensen D.H., Thematic analysis (2020) was an iterative method that consisted of six steps that transformed a tangle of data into a map of the data's fundamental themes. These steps were: (1) Familiarization, (2) Generating Initial Codes, (3) Theme Searching, (4) Reviewing topics, 5) Defining and Naming Themes, (6) when writing up the findings, including enough information about the study and technique for the reader to determine the quality of your work.

The thematic analysis allowed the researchers to confirm the findings. The researchers then created interpretations, conclusions, and suggestions based on the data collected.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The researchers conducted face-to-face interviews with female woodworkers to ensure that participants felt comfortable sharing information. They then presented and discussed themes based on the gathered data.

Emerged Themes	Sub Theme 1	Sub Theme 2	Sub Theme 3
Women's Role in the Woodworking Industry	Multifaceted Role of Women in Management	Women's Role in Sales and Maintenance Task	
Reasons Influencing Women's Involvement in the Woodworking	Generational Business Legacy	Household Expenditures	Poverty Alleviation
Challenges Encountered by Women in the Workplace	Difficulties Encountered due to Customer's Behavior	Difficulties Encountered due to Natural Hazards	Difficulties Encountered due to the Nature of Work
Coping Strategies for Women Facing Workplace Challenges	Family Motivation	Women's Perseverance and Resiliency	
Supports and Programs for Women Workers in the Woodworking Industry	Local Government and Barangay Initiatives	Women Undecided due to time Availability	Women Willing to Participate in Personal and Professional Growth

THEME 1. WOMEN'S ROLES IN THE WOODWORKING INDUSTRY

Sub-theme 1.1: Multifaceted Role of Women in Management

Multifaceted refers to having several facets, aspects, or phases. It means that someone plays numerous roles in addition to their primary one. Employees frequently take on multiple tasks for efficiency, but sometimes, it may not be their decision. However, being flexible can be beneficial. Having the knowledge and skills to fulfill many responsibilities in a single job has proven advantageous. This capacity reduces the need to wait for someone else to finish a task, which increases overall productivity (Kindall, 2018).

The researchers asked the participants about the roles they perform in the woodworking industry.

According to **WP2**, their family owns the furniture business, and she has been hired as a manager, performing other tasks besides managing it. *"Sometimes what I do here is sanding, varnishing, and rattan weaving..."* she spoke." How do you view the specific duties given to you? She answered, *"For now, I just observe the workers first, and then when they finish their orders, I help to lighten their workload by doing things like sanding and varnishing."*

WP5 states that she is the manager and also handles other tasks.

"I do varnish and repairs when there are issues with orders. Also responsible for handling the ordering process, and so I serve as the manager here."

WP6 answered, *"First, in this kind of furniture business, I handle sales, then cleaning, assisting customers, and helping the workers."* "Are you the owner of this furniture shop or the manager?"

"I have a big boss; I am the manager here." she spoke.

Lastly, **WP9** is also the manager of the furniture store. *"I assist, manage, monitor the needed materials, and also handle marketing. I also help with varnishing."*

Concerning in a modern organization, a manager has several responsibilities, including budgetary planning and management. Manager is someone who works inside an organization's framework, is motivated by predetermined goals, and is responsible for combining production factors in a way that maximizes output. (The Multifaceted Role of a Manager, 2015)

On the other hand, research conducted by Pew Research Center on women and leadership indicates that many women are often more adept at empathy and problem-solving than man. However, there are few differences between the sexes in key leadership domains such as creativity and invention. In every sector, numerous attributes of female leadership are equally significant to those of male leadership. It discovered that organizations with female managers have more financial well-being.

Sub-theme 1.2: Women's Role in Sales and Maintenance Tasks

A sale is the process of selling products and services. It entails persuading potential clients to buy from the business. Convincing can be accomplished through various methods, including discussing the positive features of the product, offering discounts, or making the product more appealing than competitors' (Indeed, 2024).

On the other hand, maintenance cleaning includes routine chores that go beyond daily cleaning. It follows a set schedule and often involves inspecting, cleaning, washing, replacing, and checking. These services focused on preserving and increasing the lifespan of different things within a business (*SafetyCulture*, 2024).

The researchers asked about the roles of the participants in woodworking.

"...I maintain the cleanliness of the furniture, teach the tasks to the polishers or the varnishers, and follow up on the orders."
(WP3)

"Here, I engage in sales conversations with customers and ensure the cleanliness of the furniture we are selling. When customers arrive, I communicate with them and provide assistance in finding what they are looking for, ultimately aiming to make a sale." **(WP4)**

"I handle cleaning and engage in sales conversations when there are customers. I work as a saleswoman here. So, it is important to maintain cleanliness in this industry." **(WP7)**

"...I handle both cleaning and sales. As a saleswoman, I am responsible for engaging with customers and providing assistance. I also take care of the cleaning tasks, and when there are customers, I'm the one who talks with them." **(WP8)**

The participant's responses emphasized their roles in sales and maintenance tasks within the furniture industry. Through their expertise in various responsibilities such as sales talk, customer assistance, cleanliness, and managing orders, these women make invaluable contributions to the woodworking industry.

Relating to this, the Office of Congressional Workplace Rights (2024) emphasizes that keeping the workplace clean ensures workplace safety. When the workplace is not kept clean and organized, risks and unsafe circumstances might arise, causing a significant risk not only to the employee but also to those surrounding the area. The workplace and nature of the work determine what is required to ensure safe working conditions.

Moreover, a 2021 study conducted in the United States by Xactly found that women make 29% of sales representatives and 26% of sales managers, despite being proven to outperform their male colleagues (Barrett, 2023). Sales proficiency extends beyond mastering the fundamentals of business transactions. It is about engaging with clients on a deeper level, understanding their needs, and delivering solutions that speak to their deepest desires. This expertise has the potential to transform the careers of women in business. It has the potential to transform a start-up into a successful business and an idea into a movement. However, obtaining this level of expertise usually requires assistance, guidance, and a group that believes in one's abilities (Griffith, 2024).

THEME 2. REASONS INFLUENCING WOMEN'S INVOLVEMENT IN THE WOODWORKING

Sub-theme 2.1: Generational Business Legacy

A family business represents more than just an economic entity that generates wealth. It is a harmonic blend of family values, a legacy, and a vision passed down through successive generations. Legacy businesses stand out for their long history and generational leadership, which have survived economic cycles, technological advancements, and market changes. These businesses are more than surviving enterprises; they represent resilience, adaptation, and the ability to foresee and shape the future (getbestbusinesscoach.com, 2023).

The researchers asked the participants about the reasons that influenced their decisions to enter the woodworking industry.

"In our barangay, this has always been the traditional job and business, so we have been doing this for a very long time."
(WP2)

"Before, my father used to take care of it, but he passed away, and no one else wanted to manage it. So as a woman, I took it upon myself." (WP5)

Family-owned businesses are among the most successful businesses in the world, and they contribute considerably to each country's economy. Family ties and customs strongly influence the culture of family firms. Woman-owned family enterprises are prospering and transforming the face of family businesses worldwide.

More women have joined the family business today; their numbers will continue to increase. Women have many opportunities in family business, with over 60% of all family-owned enterprises having women in top executive positions. Women have recently not only inherited the firm but have also become actively involved in its operation. Today, more women are active in family businesses, showcasing greater abilities than ever (Kothari & Tobwala, *n.d.*).

Sub-theme 2.2: Household Expenditures

Household expenses are a breakdown of general living expenses per person, including lodging, food consumed at home, utilities, child education, and other costs (Kagan, 2022).

"For our daily expenses and for my child's education." (WP1)

"Of course, it's for my children, to support their education and cover expenses. When I get my salary, I buy rice and other household necessities." (WP4)

"For my family, so we have money for daily expenses." (WP6)

"...So, I can give my child allowance and pay the electricity bill." (WP8)

Based on the responses from our participants, four of them stated that their reasons for entering the woodworking industry were to earn money, contribute to their families, and meet their daily expenses.

Under these circumstances, a survey conducted by IndiaLends among over 10,000 working women aged 24-55 in metropolitan, tier 1, and tier 2 cities revealed that more than 90% of respondents contribute to household expenses, with over 40% providing more than half of their income (Ray, 2024).

Moreover, women are key economic actors, as they produce and process food for their families, care for children, the elderly, and the sick, and dedicate their income and labor to their children's education, health, and well-being. Research shows that mothers typically spend their income on food and healthcare for their children, while men tend to allocate a larger portion of their income to personal needs. A study conducted in Brazil found that a child's survival probability in metropolitan areas is more than 20 times higher when the household income is managed by a woman rather than a man (Gupta, 2012).

Sub-theme 2.3: Poverty alleviation

Poverty alleviation seeks to improve the quality of life for individuals who now live in poverty (IGI Global, *n.d.*).

"One of the reasons I began working here is to lift us out of poverty..." (WP7)

"For my child's future, so I can support their education and lift us out of poverty." (WP3)

Primarily, women tend to be more focused on securing their financial future. They are more likely to save money, plan for retirement, and consider the well-being of their families and children. A regular salary allows them to put these plans into effect (Meyers, 2022).

THEME 3. CHALLENGES ENCOUNTERED BY WOMEN IN THE WORKPLACE

Sub-theme 3.1: Difficulties Encountered Due to Customer's Behavior

Customer behavior refers to the actions, choices, and preferences of individuals when engaging with products or services. This includes factors like purchasing habits, attitudes, and brand loyalty. Understanding consumer behavior is important for businesses because it helps them design products and services that meet the needs and desires of their target audience. It also enables them to develop marketing strategies that effectively communicate the value of their offerings to potential customers. (Storyly, *n.d.*)

The researchers asked the participants about the challenges they encountered or experienced.

"...But sometimes, it's really difficult to understand customers because they constantly follow up on their orders without understanding our situation. Some may even back out after the item has already been made. And although it may be their fault, we still take responsibility, which can be stressful." (WP3)

"Sometimes, when a customer is in a hurry and gets angry because the delivery wasn't made on time due to rain..." (WP5)

"I guess the challenge for me that I can't avoid is when a customer rejects the delivery, especially if there's a small mistake or damage, they really get upset." (WP6)

"We experienced being scammed, and another challenge for us is dealing with customers who constantly complaining." (WP9)

One of the most crucial aspects of managing a business is customer alignment. According to Milanovic et al. (2016), a company's ability to connect with its customers is a key factor in determining its success. Additionally, Schaefer et al. (2016) argue

that customer misconduct in service environments is troublesome for two reasons: first, it causes direct harm; and second, it can spread to other areas, leading to serious consequences.

Sub-theme 3.2: Difficulties Encountered Due to Natural Hazards

Natural hazards are natural incidents that threaten people, property, and other things. These hazards are often predictable and tend to reoccur in the same geographic areas due to their connection with weather patterns or the physical characteristics of a region. Natural disasters, such as floods, fires, earthquakes, tornadoes, and windstorms, affect thousands of people each year. (Maine Emergency Management Agency, *n.d.*)

"First, when the weather is hot. Second, during rain because of the flooding here and the lack of drainage, that's all." (WP2)

What steps are taken in the event of a flood here?

"We lift the wood and other items because when it floods here, they just get stocked since there's no drainage, and it takes a long time to subside." (WP2)

"During rainy season, there are only a few customers and it floods here too." (WP7)

What actions are taken when flooding occurs?

"We lift the furniture here to prevent them from getting wet and damaged." (WP7)

In line with this, research by Craig et al., (2019) shows that small businesses in the U.S. are at risk from climate variability and changing weather patterns, which lead to extreme weather events and natural disasters. This is particularly true in the southeastern U.S. coastal regions, where extreme weather events like thunderstorms, flooding, and hurricanes are expected to occur more frequently and with greater intensity. This growing challenge raises concerns about small businesses' ability to adapt to climate change-induced extreme weather, such as hurricanes. According to the Federal Emergency Management Agency (2015), between 40% and 60% of small businesses that experience a natural disaster never reopen.

Sub-theme 3.3: Difficulties Encountered Due to the Nature of the Work

The nature of work refers to the essential features, characteristics, and fundamental aspects that constitute a specific job or task. It includes the duties to be carried out, routine tasks, and any additional responsibilities that may arise throughout the day. (John Clements Consultants, 2024)

"...There are fewer customers now, so we only work on the orders we receive. I also need to lift heavy items like chairs here" (WP1)

"Here, we move and lift heavy items that women can't handle." (WP4)

"... When I clean, I also need to lift the furniture that I can handle. A challenge I face is that sometimes there are very few customers, resulting in slow sales." (WP8)

For this reason, the study of Horrevorts et al. (2018) has shown a strong correlation between employees' reported productivity and objective cleanliness in the offices of non-profit organizations in the Netherlands. A substantial correlation has been found between employees' work satisfaction levels in office environments and higher levels of cleanliness. Additionally, a strong relationship exists between workers' perceived productivity and their overall satisfaction with their work. Higher satisfaction levels are associated with higher perceptions of productivity.

THEME 4. COPING STRATEGIES FOR WOMEN FACING WORKPLACE CHALLENGES

Sub-theme 4.1: Family Motivation

Family motivation, defined as the desire to work to support one's family (Menges et al., 2017), is an important aspect of the workplace that inspires employees to perform effectively and efficiently to support their families in a variety of workplace settings (Tariq & Ding, 2018); it grows stronger when the employee's family is on a tight financial budget.

"I will just sleep to avoid stress; I will endure it for my family." (WP1)

"Of course, I will endure it for my children, they are my inspiration for why I strive to work hard..." (WP3)

"Of course, I need to fight for my family." (WP4)

"My family becomes my inspiration..." (WP6)

"My children become my motivation to keep going." (WP9)

The participants expressed a strong sense of family motivation, emphasizing the importance of working to support their families financially. Their commitment to their families acts as a driving force, motivating them to work harder despite challenges. This highlights the important role family plays in inspiring individuals to persevere in the workplace.

In this context, when intrinsic and extrinsic motivational factors are lacking, employees identify 'family' as the primary and most powerful source of motivation (Menges et al., 2017; Lin et al., 2020; Zhang et al., 2020). Furthermore, they argue that familial affection plays a central role in an individual's life, significantly influencing job efficiency and effectiveness (Tariq, 2018).

Sub-theme 4.2: Women's Perseverance and Resiliency

Women demonstrate remarkable resilience and perseverance, qualities that are important during crises. Their ability to overcome obstacles, maintain a positive outlook, and endure hardship serves as an indicator of hope and strength for those around them, helping others navigate difficult circumstances (Radulovski, 2024).

"I manage to endure it because we support and help each other here, and as long as you are hardworking and patient, you can overcome all problems." (WP2)

"I endure it simply because I have to." (WP5)

"I have to endure it for my family, especially for my children." (WP7)

"I endure it by controlling myself and singing along." (WP8)

Based on the participants' responses, the study highlights women's exceptional resilience and perseverance in the face of hardship, driven by their commitment to their families and the need to overcome challenges. Despite adversity, they demonstrate strength, creativity, and a positive attitude, becoming beacons of hope and inspiration to those around them.

Resilience is crucial for thriving amidst challenges like family issues, health crises, work pressures, and loss, impacting people of all ages and backgrounds. It is about enduring and pushing through tough times for well-being (Sisto et al., 2019).

According to Wellness (2024), women have made significant strides in the workplace. Despite numerous obstacles, they demonstrate perseverance, determination, and a commitment to advancing their careers. By leveraging their skills and strategies, women are able to overcome challenges and achieve success. Their accomplishments benefit not only themselves but also the workforce, fostering diversity and inclusion. This diversity, in turn, drives innovation and supports business growth.

THEME 5. SUPPORT AND PROGRAMS FOR WOMEN WORKERS IN WOODWORKING INDUSTRY

Sub-theme 5.1: Local Government and Barangay Initiatives

Local government units (LGUs) are crucial in ensuring the plan's provisions reach women in their areas. They are responsible for helping to implement the strategic plan by incorporating its goals and actions into the annual GAD (Gender and Development) plans, budgets, and investment plans. The Magna Carta of Women mandates local governments incorporate gender perspectives into their development plans, land use plans, and legislative agendas. These gender-inclusive strategies then guide annual investment plans and resource allocation (Philippine Commission on Women, 2014).

Additionally, the barangay, being the most accessible government unit for many Filipinos, acts as a platform for expressing, shaping, and considering collective opinions, especially by engaging underrepresented and disadvantaged groups. Barangay officials serve as the first point of contact for government services, playing a significant role in providing essential services and promoting public welfare. As a core political entity, the barangay is crucial in driving meaningful change. It also serves as the primary unit for planning and implementing government programs, policies, and projects within the community (Saligan, 2021b).

"Only relief goods, but in terms of financial assistance, I haven't noticed any programs for us either. From what I've seen on TV, it would be great if there were such programs to provide jobs for others as well." (WP2)

"I only received relief goods like rice." (WP8)

"I do not receive any assistance from the barangay or municipality." (WP1)

"I do not receive any assistance from the barangay." (WP3)

"I do not receive any assistance or see any programs here in the barangay or from the government." (WP5)

"It seems like I am not receiving or seeing any programs." (WP6)

"We have not received any assistance, and I have not seen any programs here in the barangay or the municipality either." (WP7)

"We have not received any assistance or any programs or training." (WP9)

Indeed, the women's sector was considered one of the most vulnerable in the community. As outlined in Goal 3 of the Millennium Development Goals, the regional agency and DSWD conducted training sessions, orientations, seminars, skills training, and symposiums throughout the 2015 budget year to promote the sector's rights and empower women. The Department also provided monetary assistance to help them with their needs and improve their lives (Department of Social Welfare and Development, 2015).

However, based on the responses gathered, only two individuals received relief goods, while the majority of participants reported a lack of assistance, support, or programs from the local government. This points to a concerning gap in support, with most of the community feeling overlooked or underserved.

Nonetheless, according to UNPF, to empower women, countries must take action to eliminate inequalities between men and women. This requires establishing mechanisms to ensure women's equal participation and representation in politics and public life, promoting education and skill development for women, eliminating discriminatory practices, supporting women's rights, enhancing women's economic opportunities, and eradicating violence against women.

Sub-theme 5.2: Women Undecided to Participate Due to Time Availability

The researchers asked the participants if the local government or barangay planned to undertake any programs or training and whether they would be willing to participate.

"If I have time and no work, maybe I can participate, but if there is work, of course, I would not. It really depends on the situation." (WP4)

"If I am not busy and I have available time, there is no problem, I will participate." (WP6)

"If I have time, I will participate." (WP8)

Women participants are often hesitant to join barangay and government programs due to time constraints and the fear of neglecting their work duties, particularly in sales, which could lead to consequences from their managers. However, when they have free time, they are eager to engage in such initiatives.

Research shows that women frequently struggle to prioritize and manage their time effectively due to the combined responsibilities of work, caregiving, and housework. Therefore, they may be hesitant to commit to extra activities or programs unless they are sure that they can accommodate them within their present schedules (Edlund, 2007).

Sub-theme 5.3: Women Willing to Participate for Personal and Professional Growth

"Yes, there is no problem because that is work." (WP2)

"Yes, if necessary." (WP3)

"Yes, of course, no problem." (WP5)

"Yes, I am willing because it is for my own benefit and for my improvement working in this industry." (WP7)

"Yes, of course, we are willing to participate." (WP9)

In conclusion, women are open to participating in barangay or government programs and training, as shown by their positive responses. Their willingness to engage in these initiatives demonstrates their commitment to both personal and community development despite potential challenges in balancing work responsibilities.

For this matter, according to Elvitigala et al. (2006), women pursue training programs to advance their careers, which is crucial for their professional development. A survey conducted by the World Economic Forum found that women are more confident and ambitious than ever before: 82% are confident in their capacity to achieve their job goals, 77% in their ability to lead, and 73% are actively looking for career progression opportunities. (3 Things Women Need to Succeed in Their Career – According to Women, 2020)

PROPOSED INTERVENTION PLAN FOR WOMEN'S SKILLS DEVELOPMENT AND ADDRESSING CHALLENGES IN THE WOODWORKING INDUSTRY

I. Rationale

The proposed intervention plan for women's skills development and addressing challenges in the woodworking industry is a purposeful initiative to empower women woodworkers to enhance their skills and knowledge within the sector. Recognizing the importance of gender equality and inclusivity, the "EMPOWERWOOD" program seeks to provide comprehensive training, mentorship, and resources crafted explicitly for the unique needs and challenges women face in this field. It aims to create a supportive community, facilitate access to advanced woodworking techniques, and promote skill development and economic opportunities, enabling women to achieve personal growth and secure sustainable livelihoods.

II. General Objectives

The intervention plan encompasses three primary objectives.

- To enhance participants' woodworking skills and techniques by providing comprehensive training and hands-on practice.
- To provide participants with essential knowledge and competencies to accurately recognize and mitigate natural hazards within woodworking settings, ensuring a safer working environment.
- To help enhance participants' communication abilities and customer service strategies, enabling them to address and resolve challenging customer interactions proficiently.

A Proposed Intervention Plan for Women's Skills Development and Addressing Challenges in the Woodworking Industry

Areas for Improvement	Objectives	Actions	Persons Involved	Time Frame
Enhancing Women's Woodworking Skills	Improve participants' woodworking abilities and	- Create educational materials (pamphlets, video tutorials, marketing plan, and other online	- LGU - Women woodworkers	Monthly for 6 months

	techniques through training and practice.	resources) explaining the different skills and strategies in woodworking. - Organize skill-building workshops or study groups.		
Natural Hazard Preparedness	Equip participants with the knowledge and skills necessary to identify and respond effectively to natural hazards in woodworking environments.	- Collaborate with the Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Council (DRRMC) and LGU to conduct safety training sessions. - Create emergency contact lists and an emergency response plan.	- LGU - DRRMC - Women woodworkers	Safety training sessions for the first 3 months of each year
Customer Service	Enhance participants' communication skills and customer service strategies to effectively handle challenging customers.	- Host webinars and simulation training sessions to help women woodworkers develop effective customer interaction skills.	- LGU - Woodworking enterprises - Women woodworkers	Customer Service

GENERALIZATIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the comprehensive review and analysis, the following generalizations are emerged:

1. None of the participants were limited to a single role; each woman took on multiple responsibilities in the woodwork industry, including management, marketing, varnishing, sanding, maintenance, polishing, and rattan crafting. None were directly involved in the production of wood products, nor were any of them carpenters.
2. Most participants worked in woodworking to contribute to their household expenditures.
3. Most participants faced challenges due to their customers' behavior, the nature of their work, and natural hazards.
4. Most participants interviewed identified their family as their primary inspiration for overcoming challenges. In contrast, some participants emphasized their reliance on perseverance and resilience as coping strategies.
5. Some participants said they had received relief goods, while the rest had not. However, they had not seen any programs, training, or other assistance provided to them.

Based on the above generalizations, the following recommendations arise:

1. The Technical Education and Skills Development Authority (TESDA) may actively promote women's participation in skills development programs, with a particular focus on carpentry courses. In addition, ensuring these courses are accessible and welcoming to women will help encourage greater involvement.
2. The Local Government Unit may provide financial literacy programs and access to microfinance opportunities to help women meet their household expenses and alleviate poverty. Also, offering business development support and resources can help women in family businesses enhance their skills, expand their operations, and achieve sustainable growth.
3. Barangay officials may work with the Local Government Unit and the Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Office to prioritize improving and maintaining drainage systems in flood-prone areas, which will help minimize the impact of floods on businesses. They may also create and share emergency response plans for natural disasters, including strategies to safeguard materials, equipment, and products, as well as provide training sessions to ensure businesses are fully prepared.
4. Local officials may facilitate forming peer support groups or women's organizations where women can share coping strategies and provide mutual support.
5. Local Government Units (LGUs) may advocate for policies that support women in the woodwork industry, including subsidies or grants targeted at small businesses and female entrepreneurs/employees. They may also offer tailored programs and training to meet the specific needs of women in this sector, helping to enhance their skills and capabilities.

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